

RESHORING AND SUPPLY CHAIN SUSTAINABILITY: STRATEGIES FOR BUILDING RESILIENT OPERATIONS

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Abstract. *The paper highlights reshoring's critical role in making supply chains resilient, sustainable, and effective. It identifies Industry 4.0 technologies like automation, digital twins, and blockchain that help in lowering logistical complexities to make domestic production affordable. It also explores key enablers like government incentives, public-private partnership, and advanced manufacturing systems that are critical in addressing the challenges of workforce upskilling, supply network reconstruction, and policy alignment. The paper situates reshoring as a strategic solution in attaining adaptive, sustainable, and competitive supply chains by analyzing these elements. This is most pertinent within the context of increasingly disrupting global events and the potential need for long-term resilience.*

Keywords: *reshoring, Supply Chain Innovation, Engineering Optimization, Supply Chain Resilience, Advanced Manufacturing Technologies, Industry 4.0 Innovations.*

Introduction. Over the last decade, there has been a radical change in the global supply chain environment. While for years offshoring had been one of the key strategies pursued by many firms, there is an increasing momentum—on the part of business leaders and policymakers alike—for reshoring today. Indeed, over the last two decades, companies in the First World outsourced their manufacturing and production-related processes to the Third World in a bid to exploit low-cost labor. However, they retained key operations which required specialized expertise and huge amounts of resources within their own national boundaries.

This offshoring trend gave way to integrated systems, popularly known as GVCs, which from then on formed the backbone of modern supply chains. However, the analysis done by UNCTAD in 2024 both sketched and updated the contours on how economic shifts are now rewriting these networks and rewriting international production models [i]. By the 2010s, this dominance of offshoring began to falter, which showed great change in GVCs. The three main causes underpinning this shift have included the increasing need for a supply chain that is resilient, less reliance on low-cost labor due to continuous improvement in robotics and automation, and a greater interest in sustainability, apart from policy reforms. All these forces combined are, therefore, creating conditions conducive to companies relocating production closer to home and once again redefining the global supply chain landscape.

Technology development is an essential step toward reshoring because it liberates the firm from dependency on low-wage labor and accomplishes the task of keeping its costs competitive with robotics, automation, and digital tools. Thus, domestic production is feasible and responsive to fluctuating market needs when such innovations contribute to higher productivity and robustness in supply chains. Other studies also show support for the fact that Industry 4.0 technologies are considered critical to this reshoring movement [ii]. In addition, it is only now that

locating plants in developed countries has become economically feasible in those industries where labor costs are higher as a result of advances in the automation of processes[iii].

With recent global events such as trade wars, conflicts, the pandemic, and increasing logistics costs, reshoring could only have gained momentum in both reaction to challenges from being offshore and in a proactive search for strengthening supply chains against future disruptions. This trend is significantly gaining momentum in Europe and the United States, while companies are increasingly recognizing reshoring as beneficial for both strategic resilience and sustainability[iv].

Moreover different researchers such as Ben L. Kedia and Mukherjee et al.[v] or Lo and Hung[vi] represent just a few among many who have extensively contributed to the literature on offshoring. Although significant advancements have been made in the realm of offshoring, there is a growing recognition that equal emphasis is needed on reshoring to adapt to evolving economic and strategic demands.

Relocation strategies encompass returning activities to the home country, moving them to a nearby region, or shifting them to a distant new location. This study centers on the approach of bringing operations back to the home country. However, the insights may also be relevant to cases where companies choose nearby regions with similar economic and social conditions to those of the home country.

Literature Review and Methods. This research employs a qualitative data analysis approach, integrating insights from existing literature on reshoring and Industry 4.0 technologies. Data sources include academic journals, government reports, and case studies from sectors affected by reshoring. This research is in IMRAD format and is presenting both the objectives of research with the identification of key drivers of the reshoring trend by systematic analysis. Reviews of recent related studies have been made with a view to classify motivations for reshoring, understand the development of technological advantage, assess economic outcome, and its outcome on sustainability.

Amongst those reshoring cases, the U.S.CHIPS and Science Act[vii] was constituted into law to further reinforce American supply chains in a geopolitically tight environment. This decision mirrors a wide global trend for the reshoring of supplies in order to increase the resilience of one's supply chain while protecting one's own national interests.

In 2023, American manufacturers started building new facilities at record rates, with the lion's share of that activity going to semiconductors, food processing, chemicals, and plastics. Along with that came a spate of "nearshoring" as U.S. companies expanded operations to Mexico and other nearby countries, as well as "friend-shoring" of production to politically allied nations. Options that have even greater resonance in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, where reshoring forms one of the important tools for improving business resilience and operational stability [viii].

Reshoring is also an increasingly greater opportunity to contribute to sustainable supply chains, mainly through a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by reason of shorter transport ways [ix]. This activity supports global environmental commitments and underlines a growing corporate concern for reducing ecological footprints.

More importantly, reshoring aligns with the emerging trend of consumers to increasingly favor brands that represent their cultural identity and values. The interaction of local and global values, moderated by brand identification, leads to a marked preference for either locally rooted

or globally recognized products [x]. This development is an indication of how the dynamics of consumer behavior are shifting and how this impacts supply chain strategies. Consumer perception analysis shows that reshoring contributes to national sustainability goals in economic, social, and environmental dimensions [xi]. Economically speaking, reshoring can help consumers support local businesses and develop a national economy, thus reducing dependence on imports and probably increasing product prices. Socially, reshoring is viewed as a means to create jobs, enhance skills, and uplift community morale, though it could potentially disrupt local areas and increase income inequality. The so-called *Multiplier Effect** underscores how reshoring amplifies economic benefits by creating a ripple of local growth. By relocating production back home, companies generate employment, bolster local suppliers, and increase demand for supporting services. This snowball effect triggers consumer spending, boosts regional growth, and strengthens supply chains in the country, making reshoring not only a strategic business decision but also one for long-term economic growth.

According to the National Association of Manufacturers, each dollar invested in the manufacturing sector generates approximately \$2.60 in economic value for the greater economy [xii]. This makes explicit the strong multiplier effect that manufacturing has on supporting industries, local businesses, and even the community itself, further placing the sector at the heart of economic prosperity and resilience.

Environmentally, consumers appreciate that reshoring can reduce emissions by shortening shipping distances but recognize that it may also lead to local pollution and added strain on ecosystems due to increased manufacturing activity.

For some scholars, reshoring is a strategic revocation of the earlier offshoring decisions. It is not necessary that returning of all offshore operations or closure of an entire facility takes place. In fact, it gives a firm the choice of relocating partial functions or segments of production. In principle, reshoring can be portrayed as a location decision that can be approached in isolation from the ownership structure. This also reflects flexibility in terms of adjusting to changing economic and operational requirements[xiii].

Graph - 1. FDI Job Announcement by Year (2010-2023)

It would be instructive to track data on the reshoring process, particularly in the United States, which has been a long-standing initiator of Chinese offshoring policies dating back to the late 1980s. Beginning in 2010, FDI and job repatriation efforts have taken a key turn. According

to 2023 data from the Reshoring Initiative [xiv], this 13-year path has seen roughly two million jobs return to the U.S., reflecting a significant reversal in offshoring trends.

Note: **The Multiplier Effect* - an economic phenomenon wherein any initial investment or activity, such as reshoring, triggers a chain reaction in increased spending and job creation to amplify the effect on the local economy.

Reshoring attempts also can be seen by a surge in U.S. manufacturing construction, making it the fastest-growing property sector. According to the U.S. Census Bureau, spending reached \$114.7 billion in 2022—a 40% year-over-year increase and 62% over five years [xv].

Graph – 2. USA Manufacturing Construction Spending (2017-2023)

Various researchers have investigated motives in the context of the U.S. market that have driven various push and pull forces on reshoring decisions [xvi]. The following table depicts those factors, thus giving a more detailed view of the elements affecting reshoring strategies.

Push and Pull Factors for Reshoring

Push factors (discouraging offshore)	Pull factors (encouraging reshoring)
Loss of Know-How and Risk of IP Theft	Lower Energy Costs
Narrowing Labor Cost Advantages	Investments in Automation Technologies
High Total Costs of Sourcing, Transportation, and Oversight	Proximity to R&D Facilities
Relaxed Environmental Regulations	
Reduced Corporate Tax Rates	

One study revealed that the most prevalent strategy among the articles was a general approach to adopting new technologies, which appeared in 46% of the studies. This widespread focus on broad technology adoption suggests that many organizations prioritize integrating advanced tools and systems as a foundational strategy, without necessarily specifying particular technologies [xvii]. This trend underscores an emphasis on staying technologically adaptable and open to various innovations to enhance overall capabilities.

Van Den Bossche et al.[xviii] underscore critical reshoring challenges for U.S. manufacturers, emphasizing that much of the domestic supplier network has shifted abroad, making it difficult to secure local, cost-effective suppliers. They also highlight an aging manufacturing workforce with younger generations less inclined or equipped to fill these roles, especially as advanced manufacturing processes become more prevalent. Addressing these issues

will require substantial market adaptation, as reshored jobs will demand a modern, highly skilled workforce quite different from traditional manufacturing.

The Advanced Manufacturing Partnership [xix] highlights several key technology areas that could indirectly support reshoring efforts by bolstering U.S. manufacturing capabilities. Innovations in sensors, process control, and digital modeling tools, like CAD and 3D printing, allow for efficient, adaptable production. Sustainable manufacturing, through energy-efficient processes and automation, minimizes waste and aligns well with domestic environmental standards. Meanwhile, advancements in nano-manufacturing, flexible electronics, and bio-manufacturing enhance production for high-tech products, potentially making domestic manufacturing more feasible and competitive.

Some studies indicate that reshoring can play a crucial role in advancing sustainability objectives, particularly by reducing environmental impacts linked to long-distance transportation and offshore production practices [xx]. This strategy aligns with broader climate goals by supporting decarbonization and fostering more localized, sustainable production systems. Researchers have suggested that reshoring strengthens the reliability of supply chains and encourages clean and resource-efficient manufacturing practices, reinforcing relevance to sustainable development.

Reshoring is considered one avenue to enhance resilience in supply chains by reducing dependence on international suppliers, enabling response times to become shorter and quality and compliance controls to be tighter. Companies that move their operations closer to home can achieve shorter lead times, faster delivery, and enhanced flexibility to the market's demands. Moreover, reshoring reduces the threat of intellectual property theft and creates a safer place for being innovative, establishing supply chains that are resilient and agile [xxi].

Results. Based on the reviewed materials, a number of strategies could be identified to create resilience in reshoring operations. These strategies can be divided into two groups: Traditional and Industry 4.0. The first group includes strategies related to the strengthening of the stability of supply chains by means such as in-house production, building redundancy with domestic suppliers, maintaining local inventory, and enhancing workforce skills. These strategies enhance control of supply chain components and reduce dependence on others. In contrast, Industry 4.0 strategies leverage flexible manufacturing systems; IoT and AI for real-time insights; digital twins for simulation; and blockchain for secure tracking. Together, the strategies prepare companies to design resilient and adaptable supply chains that are more resilient against disruptions.

Graph – 3. Reshoring Resilience Strategies

Discussions. *Traditional Strategies*: Effective inventory management is a critical aspect of reshoring, and careful consideration should be given to the most appropriate approaches. In this

context, in-house production, when affordable, serves as a primary or backup source, reducing reliance on external suppliers. Dual sourcing, combining reliable and cost-effective suppliers, balances risk and cost but may be best replaced by single sourcing from a reliable supplier when capacity is limited. Downward substitution allows flexibility, either by substituting high-quality components in supply gaps or reallocating resources under capacity constraints [xxii].

Training is the key to reshoring for a company, laying the foundation for the successful integration of activities in the home country. The company should provide broad training for the workforce to upskill them in new technologies, smooth workflow, and quality improvement. Emphasis on workforce preparedness will definitely help the teams to manage the complexities of reshoring and can adapt swiftly to the operational changes it entails [xxiii].

Equally important is a thorough assessment of the company's current resources and competencies to gauge readiness for reshoring. Companies benefit from conducting audits to identify strengths, gaps, and opportunities within their operations, such as technological capacity, skilled labor, and supply chain relationships [xxiv]. Developing partnerships with educational institutions can further enrich the talent pool, while fostering internal collaboration aligns all departments along with reshoring goals. These all put together create one comprehensive strategy that trains and strategically evaluates the approach for resilience and growth by bringing operations back home.

Reshoring manufacturing continues to depend on the availability of significant government incentives, including subsidies, tax breaks, and grants. These incentives offset some of the relocation costs, foster innovation, and contribute to keeping supply chains domestic, thus making it all worthwhile and more viable for companies to reshore. Through these incentives, help governments create a competitive manufacturing industry to support the economy and reinforce national interest in strategic industries [xxv]. As such, the U.S. Innovation and Competition Act and its recent counterpart, the CHIPS and Science Act gave a major stimulus to the reshoring activity in recent times, particularly for semiconductors. Targeted subsidies and funding for research, design, and U.S. production of semiconductors were given through these acts. With these two acts, reshoring agencies eased part of the financial costs and, therefore, have been instrumental in revitalizing local manufacturing, reinforcing national supply chains, and strengthening the foundation for U.S.-based production in strategic sectors.

*Public-private partnerships*** play a key role in supporting reshoring because they meld government resources with private sector capabilities. These collaborations can co-fund advanced manufacturing facilities, reducing the financial burden on businesses while enabling access to cutting-edge technologies like robotics and IoT. PPPs also foster local supplier networks and workforce development through training programs designed by collaboration, which ensures a competent labor supply in line with modern manufacturing.

Industry 4.0 Strategies: The Industry 4.0 strategies include the integration of a variety of different technologies, one of which just so happens to be blockchain: a very vital part of this reshoring strategy. The new levels of transparency that these technologies introduce mean businesses can source-trace products, observe the flow of materials, and provide certification for compliance across local networks. Example: Blockchain can enable secure, tamper-proof record-keeping, provide real-time visibility that reduces cyber risks, and therefore make the supply chain resilient. Further, blockchain-based smart contracts facilitate the process by automating payments and inventory, reducing dependence on any intermediary, catalyzing rapid speed of operation.

Technology-driven reshoring empowers corporations to build a far more robust, adaptive supply chain framework [xxvi].

The Digital twin (DT) technology, in effect, greatly influences reshoring initiatives through enhanced control and flexibility; these tend to wash away most of the challenges traditionally associated with relocation. With DT, firms can track processes across several facilities in real time. This encourages agile decision-making and frictionless collaboration—key elements for effectively adapting operations within domestic settings [xxvii].

Cloud-based platforms using DTs and cyber-physical systems can give full insights into production and logistics. These allow firms to act dynamically toward any market fluctuation and operational disruption; hence, this would give way to a smoother transition and reduce the risk of reshoring [xxviii]. DT has led to the operational efficiency which streamlined key functions, including product design, production planning, and predictive maintenance, and developed reshored manufacturing resilience, thus building sustainable competitiveness in local markets [xxix].

Enriched supply chain visibility is key to enhancing the efficiency of manufacturing, transactional processes, planning, supply management, and performance assessment [xxx]. Good visibility allows for a more integrated perspective of operations, which is essential to companies that are looking to bring production back onshore. The ultimate objective of supply chain visibility is the development of enterprise performance by offering real-time access to operational information of high importance and foresight enabling strategic decisions [xxxi]. This is especially crucial in the case of reshoring, as it offers a means of tracking and optimization for each stage of the production process and logistics domestically, bringing down delays, offering better control over inventories, and thereby making supply chains more responsive locally.

Note: ***Public-Private Partnerships* – PPPs are a collaboration between government and private entities to fund and manage projects, sharing risks and benefits.

Strong visibility tools will enable firms to ensure that reshoring operations are cost-effective, robust, agile—that is, quick to adapt to changes either in demand or supply chain disruptions. That will mean a much larger number of self-sustaining, transparent supply chains—which corresponds well with the aims of reshoring initiatives by establishing a sound foundation for local stability and competitiveness of production.

That is the point where intelligent manufacturing currently stands on the way to enabling reshoring by solving some problems that in the past barred companies from relocating their operations back to their home countries. Zhang et al. (2017) discuss how the implementation of such technological advantages as AI-driven decisions, robotics, Industrial IoT, and smart sensors turn reshoring as a much more competitive and viable strategy. These technologies further facilitate automation and operational efficiencies, effectively offsetting higher labor costs that are normally associated with domestic production. In addition, smart manufacturing offers flexibility in the production process—one that can easily respond to fluctuating market demands and customer preferences. In addition, it is a vital component in justifying reshoring investment decisions.

Other relevant applications identified by Zhang et al. (2017) include those of smart ISO STEP in manufacturing systems to guarantee interoperability between different systems for easy production and integration of supply chains after relocation. Other sophisticated tools, such as product lifecycle testing, enhance quality while limiting the production of waste, adding value to

reshoring companies. Moreover, agent-based intelligent manufacturing systems, as noted in their work, ensure resource optimization and maximize productivity, allowing operations to be economical even in regions with high labor costs. Generally, all the concepts developed by Zhang et al. Among them, intelligent manufacturing should be regarded as a driver that fosters economic feasibility, supply chain resilience, and sustainability, thus acting strategically to enable reshoring within the worldwide manufacturing context.

Fundamental elements and applications of intelligent manufacturing:

Concepts	Major Characteristics	Supporting Technologies	Applications
Intelligent Manufacturing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AI-driven decision-making - Advanced automation - Flexible manufacturing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Big data - Robotics - Industrial IoT - Smart sensors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart manufacturing systems with ISO STEP - Product life-cycle testing - Agent-based IMS

Source: Zhong, R. Y., et al.[xxxii]

Cost-Benefit Analysis for Reshoring Viability: In addition, one main factor in reshoring is the economic viability against producing goods offshore. A handy formula that can be used here is the Net Cost Savings, which compares the sum of operational costs offshore and onshore, adjusted for initial investment and transition expenses related to reshoring. This can be expressed as:

$$\text{Net Cost Savings} = \text{Cost of offshore} - \text{Cost of reshore} - (I_{\text{Initial}} + T_{\text{reshoring}})$$

Where:

C_{offshore} - Total operational cost offshore, including production, labor, and logistics.

C_{reshore} - Estimated total operational costs onshore.

I_{initial} - Initial investments for reshoring.

$T_{\text{reshoring}}$ - Transition costs, including employee training and developing a supplier network.

Conclusion. Reshoring is one disruptive approach in balancing economic, operational, and sustainability objectives in modern supply chains. High labor costs and operational inefficiencies, conventionally assumed, can be overcome by companies through the application of intelligent manufacturing techniques, digital twins, and even blockchain. Such enabling technologies build productivity and supply chain visibility while setting the path for smoother transitions during global turbulence.

Incentives provided by any government, like subsidies and legislative support, go a long way in defraying the cost of reshoring. Besides, such strategic measures as cost-benefit analysis, full-scale training of the workforce, and effective resource allocation give strength to a sound basis for reshoring initiatives. Reshoring decreases dependence on offshore operations, hence reducing logistics distances and thus fully satisfying the goals of sustainability for greener and more resilient supply chains.

Ultimately, reshoring will be much more than the contraction in offshoring trends but a forward-looking strategy with legs in technological innovation, policy support, and operational excellence. It readies businesses to lead through global disruptions, market forces, and sustained competitiveness within an ever-localizing greening manufacturing environment.

There are several limitations of this study. This heavily relies on secondary data, and as such, per se cannot represent the very latest developments and/or differences among industries. Qualitative in nature and insightful, it lacks the rigorous empirical basis typical of quantitative methods; hence, the analysis of economic viability would be limited under various scenarios.

The focus on advanced manufacturing and the economy that is developed, particularly U.S., may not be an indication that other industries or regions, for instance, the emerging markets, face any challenges. Another issue can be assuming that government support and policy are stable and consistent, not always able to account for geopolitical and economic uncertainty.

Further research would be of great interest if it encompassed mixed-methods, cross-industry comparative, and longitudinal data about reshoring challenges and opportunities.

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